

promising entries are given in the table. Highest survival was in IR39558-147-1-3, but because of its longer duration, most panicles did not exsert fully with high salinity and low temperature during Nov.

IR4595-4-1-13-2, IR37257-41-3-2-3, IR40578-13-2-2-3-2-2 with flowering durations of 122, 111, and 93 d, appear most promising. Considering the growth

duration suitable for local situations, IR10198-66-2-1 showed promise.

Among four local varieties tested, Hamilton was most adapted. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Performance of early Prasanna variety

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We grew 3 crops of Prasanna in sequence in 2,000 m² under restricted irrigation at Ramachandrapuram during 1986-87. Sowing was 7 Jul (normal wet season), 22 Aug (midseason), and 20

Dec (normal dry season). Twenty-day-old seedlings were planted at 15- × 15-cm spacing with moderate fertilizer (13-17 kg P-K + 40 kg N/ha). Irrigation at

10-d intervals was applied when there was no rainfall during the 10-d period.

All crops matured in 90 d (see table). Comparing the yields of the Aug and Jul sowings indicated the suitability of Prasanna for midseason planting. Total yield for the year was 8 t/ha, with a 210-d cropping period. □

Performance of Prasanna in a 3-crop year. Hyderabad, India, 1986-87.

Sowing date	Transplanting date	Maturity	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)
4 Jul	24 Jul	4 Oct	90	2.4
22 Aug	6 Sep	22 Nov	90	2.6
20 Dec	10 Jan	20 Feb	90	3.0

A high-yielding variety for coastal Andhra Pradesh, India

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MTU7014, a high-yielding, early-maturing, blast-resistant variety, is a derivative of Rasi/IR19667-131-1-2. It consistently yielded higher than BPT1235 in replicated trials during the 1985, 1986, and 1987 dry seasons (see table). In 1987 minikit farmers' field trials at 23 locations in Godavari District, MTU7014 yielded higher than local check BPT1235. □

Agronomic traits and blast resistance of MTU7014 at Maruteru, India, 1986 dry season.

Character	MTU7014	IR64	BPT 1235 (local check)
Plant type	Compact tillers dark green foliage	Compact tillers light green foliage	Low tillers, light green foliage
Growth duration (d)	125	120	120
Plant height (cm)	84	85	86
Panicles (no./m ²)	491	433	528
Spikelets (no./panicle)	99	127	93
Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	97	125	92
Sterility (%)	2.2	1.8	1.1
1000-grain weight (g)	29	28	25
Pigmentation	Green	Green	Purple
Seed dormancy (wk)	4	3	2
Reaction to blast ^a	1	1	8

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9. Tested against race IC 9.

Two new varieties from segregation material of IR36

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IR36 has a growth duration that is too long for an early rice crop in Hunan. We used it as a source of resistance

Yield, growth duration, and pest resistance of 2 new varieties in Hunan, China.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Reaction ^a to			
			BB	B1	BPH	WBPH
IR36 (female)	7.1	125	R	R	R	-
Guong jei 9 (male)	-	109	S	R	S	-
Xiang Zaoxian 3	7.0	106	R	R	R	R
HA79317-4	6.6	102	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.